

Survey on BigBlueButton at universities in November 2020 by the ZKI working group Strategy & Organization

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1. Introduction

The ZKI¹ Working Group Strategy and Organization has received numerous inquiries about the use of Open Source Software in productive operation. One focus was on questions about the tool BigBlueButton² (BBB) for the implementation of video conferences. Many universities use this tool and have partly developed it further themselves. However, these developments are not yet visible at a higher level and local development capacity is also limited. The purpose of this survey is to summarize the existing development wishes for BBB in a first step, to explore possibilities for cooperation and to identify potential interested parties for joint activities. For the evaluation, the answers were partly grouped to record the frequency of responses. Where directly recognizable, product names were replaced by general information.

The survey received 56 responses.

¹ <https://www.zki.de/>

² <https://bigbluebutton.org/>

2. Summary

Of the 56 participants, 44 indicate that they would like to operate a BigBlueButton installation productively or would like to operate BBB for their own university. The size of the installations varies greatly - from testing with a few servers to supplying a federal state with up to 4,000 simultaneous users in up to 400 conferences with 180 servers.

The top 10 most frequently mentioned feature areas for further developments is

Number of entries	Feature
12	Meetings with more participants
11	Scalability
10	Session recording
9	Audio quality
9	Improve breakout rooms
9	Weak clients must not pull down the VC
6	Stability Improvements
6	Virtual background or blur
5	Usability
4	Diagnostic possibilities for users
3	Current Linux version
3	Better update policies
2	Better survey tool
2	Improve installation
2	Fast echo check
2	whiteboard

On the question of concrete financial support for BBB projects, 23 participants clearly expressed their willingness to support such activities. The amounts mentioned vary between 1.000€ and 50.000€ with the average of the nominations being about 11.000€.

3. Catalog of questions

The following questions were asked:

1.

Are you already using BBB productively or do you intend to use it?

Answer options: Free text

2.

Please tell us your biggest needs for improvements, new features or bugfixes of BigBlueButton with decreasing priority.

Answer options: Free text

3.

Would you participate in joint development projects? If so, what financial contribution could you make to a jointly coordinated development?

Answer options: Free text

4.

Would you like to be included in the list of interested parties for BBB activities?

Answer options: Yes, No, comment

4. Evaluation of the questions

1. Are you already using BBB productively or do you intend to use it?

This question was answered by 55 participants.

The overwhelming majority of 44 participants stated that they already use BBB productively or plan to use it productively. 11 responses indicated that they did not plan to use BBB productively.

Some answers also indicated how many servers BBB is running on.

Figure 1: Number of servers for the BBB installation

The following comments were also made:

Yes, productive, but only for small user groups. The resource requirements on the end devices are too high for larger groups
Yes, but BBB is a niche product and in my opinion it will remain so for the broad online teaching, because the complete online teaching (under Corona) for a university cannot be operated economically through it.
only in a pilot plant
Yes and yes (15 pure BBB server+scalite+stun+...) connected to moodle with plugin
We use BBB on a very small scale for special needs (committee meetings), but an expansion is planned.
yes, 10 servers virtualized with load balancer
No, at present centrally only as a test system. Also decentralized (computer science) as a rented external (self-administered) server.
Yes, currently about 180 BBB servers for universities, colleges and schools in Rhineland-Palatinate. On weekdays about 400 conferences with more than 4000 participants:inside at the same time.
productive for almost all courses, integrated in Moodle
No, we do not use BBB yet. We are currently using other solutions but would like to observe the use of BBB at universities and see BBB as a possible Schrems2 exit scenario for other solutions.
There is no deployment at the moment. However, in the course of Schrems-II conceivable.
BBB is not in use at the University of Basel. Due to the frequent use at German universities, I have discussed among colleagues from Swiss universities whether a cooperation based on BBB is conceivable. The resonance was very low, because it is assumed - probably without knowledge of the system - that an open source solution cannot compete with other solutions in terms of

<p>stability, scalability, functionality and especially usability and would not be accepted by the users. We are not planning to go it alone. Nevertheless, I am interested in receiving more detailed information about development and deployment and would possibly take up the topic again.</p>
<p>We have installed 3 BBB servers and the balancer Scalelite at KU Eichstätt. As frontend we currently only have ILIAS (plugin). We introduced it as a test phase for the winter semester and it is available to all lecturers. We want to decide around January whether we will continue with it.</p>
<p>Yes, we run three instances for the University of Paderborn: - a cluster of four blades, mainly for online teaching, room creation only for staff and lecturers- a VM with access for students- a VM without admission possibilities, especially for committee work</p>
<p>currently in productive use (4 servers + load balancer + monitoring)</p>
<p>BBB is currently not used productively. A future use is currently being investigated in a university-wide survey.</p>
<p>BBB is currently used for research and teaching.</p>
<p>Productive use since April 2020</p>
<p>In use since April 2020 Now as a cluster. Due to the very scarce personnel situation in the RZ, we manage the BBB (and Rocket Chat and Jitsi and OpenCast) together with the company SSystems from Berlin (www.ssystems.de) Good partner!</p>
<p>Used as central sales tool, with and without Moodle connection.</p>
<p>We have been using BBB since March with a link to our LMS Stud.IP, at the suggestion of data-quest (support service provider). After teething problems with a single server, a cluster was set up, which streams/records in several instances and renders in one and can be extended if necessary. Thanks to the preparatory work of data-quest, a guideline for the use of BBB together with the administrative functions of Stud.IP, which was adapted to our university, could be created in a very short time. This guideline is used intensively by the teaching staff and thus reduces the support effort considerably.</p>
<p>Use only experimentally within the RZ. The IT steering committee has focused on other solutions</p>
<p>The Faculty of Computer Science at TUM has been using BBB productively since the beginning of the summer semester 2020.</p>
<p>in use since may/june 2020</p>
<p>We use BBB productively on two nodes for teaching at a faculty.</p>
<p>No, not currently. We use other solutions and DFN-Conf</p>
<p>We have been using BBB since July this year.</p>
<p>We have introduced BBB in a pilot project with a service provider for an initial one year period to complement JITSU, other solutions and DFNconf and are testing it in combination with Moodle (and OpenCast). The main goal is to consolidate various video conferencing/webinar platforms within an integrated technical and service infrastructure to support digital teaching and to prioritize technology, further development and application support accordingly.</p>
<p>We use BBB in addition to other solutions for digital teaching, digital events and consulting. We operate several BBB clusters with and without recording functions. Greenlight is used as front-end.</p>
<p>Yes, currently with about 500 parallel users on several virtual servers</p>
<p>Yes, since the summer semester 2020 BBB is an integral part of teaching; i.e. integration into the learning platform ILIAS, coupling to OpenCast as well as general access via Greenlight including LDAP authentication. The BBB cluster is dimensioned and optimized to map the entire virtual teaching. Hessian universities can also use the UMR's BBB cluster via the Hessian digLL project (https://www.digll-hessen.de). Access is via Shibboleth authentication (https://webconf.digll-hessen.de/b/).</p>
<p>Yes, since March 2020 with success on VMs and hardware servers as primary VK system</p>

2. Please tell us your biggest needs for improvements, new features or bugfixes of BigBlueButton with decreasing priority.

There were 51 answers to this question.

The most frequently mentioned feature requests are:

Number of entries	Feature
12	Meetings with more participants
11	Scalability
10	Session recording
9	Audio quality
9	Improve breakout rooms
9	Weak clients must not pull down the VC
6	Stability Improvements
6	Virtual background or blur
5	Usability
4	Diagnostic possibilities for users
3	Current Linux version
3	Better update policies
2	Better survey tool
2	Improve installation
2	Fast echo check
2	whiteboard

The nominations on place 1 were

Integration of telephone dial-up
Resource requirements on the end devices too high, only relatively up-to-date and powerful devices allow for low-disturbance participation
Scalability
- Audio quality
Meetings with > 50 participants
- Recording option in compliance with data protection regulations, if necessary via Opencast (https://weblog.lkiesow.de/20200318-integrate-bigbluebutton-opencast/), recording and processing preferably external
Support of current infrastructure / operating systems
- better scaling with the number of video streams (maybe similar to Jitsi Videobridge) - people want to turn on the webcams and see each other, they are used to that as standard from other platforms
- Possibility to work with larger groups of participants (more than 200 participants) (see problems at the ILIAS DE conference)
New load distribution algorithm for Scalelite (under development)

Stability and performance improvement, even when including end devices with weak network connection / low performance
Scaling for large groups,
Stability improvement of the current version (2.2.28)
Improved survey tool (more question types, more options)
- Stability and availability
- Quality in audio and video, as there is often noise
Increase of the maximum number of participants
Statistics Features
screen sharing,
Stability
- Improving connectivity behind restrictive firewalls (TURN server)
Greenlight also with docker
-Export presentations with created sketches to BBB.
-Sort server rooms by status and participants in Greenlight.
Performance- Multithreading/Multitasking to achieve a better hardware utilization
Client - Background blur to hide environment
We lack the possibility to record BBB - sessions to make them available to the students.
better quality of sound and video
individual virtual image background
1. the dependence on local conditions
Group size up to 300 participants stable possible
Resynchronization of recording tracks
higher maximum number of participants
1. load balancing between BBB nodes based on parameters such as expected number of participants, not only on number of webconf per node
- definable participation limit, which cannot be overwritten by connected systems
- free choice of the install folder
1. currently the number of participants in a video conference (depending on chats, cameras, etc.) is limited to about 170 participants. This limitation occurs due to internal mechanisms of BBB and should be increased significantly.
Resource requirement client, so that conferences with multiple participants and video also work
Feature for lectures and other presentations: instead of automatic activation of the lecturer's microphone as was previously the case with BBB, manual, permanent activation of the microphone should be made possible.
integration of computer sounds
- Higher possible user numbers
* stable and reliable availability
Settings that survive a room session
1) more breakout sessions
-Securely provide records (with authorization check)
- Possibility to rename the breakout rooms
1. stronger compression of the meeting data to enable better performance even with lower bandwidth (WLAN usage)
Improvement of the sound quality (level, suppression of background noise)

- possibly accelerate release of 2.3, for example to be able to use the announced "raise hand" notification as quickly as possible
- Stability fixes for larger events
Play audio and video files directly from your local computer without having to upload them to a streaming server (in great demand!)
Scalability of the server (reliably running large events)
Poll functionalities (anonymous survey, additional question types, more than 5 answer options (already configurable))
Resource hunger, especially network load and GPU load on the clients

The nominations on place 2 are:

Improvement of the audio quality
Scalability
- Scalability
- More flexibility, e.g. quick change of microphone or webcam or the splitting/arrangement of videos or video/presentation
Greater awareness of data protection issues (recording function, mute button, deletion periods).
- Deployment as Docker-Container with Docker-Compose
- Improvement of the login process (including audio/video connection)
Fix: Fix of the stability problems introduced with 2.2.28
faster bug-fixing
More flexible breakout rooms (number, communication into the rooms)
Sound transmission for screen sharing
Manageability
IOS Sharing,
Diagnostic facility for users to identify where their connection problem lies (something like test.webrtc.org on the BBB server)
Virtual background or blur
Performance- Larger conference sizes supported / (Depends on server hardware)
higher tolerance for bandwidth fluctuations, reconnect
Image processing on separate servers
2. better behaviour in case of high server load - e.g. regulation of webcam quality based on server load up to switching off webcams
- Stability
Diagnostic facility for users to identify where their connection problem lies (something like test.webrtc.org on the BBB server)
Background selectable as with zoom
easy sharing of audios, also from TN side
- Better audio quality
* Faster changes in breakout rooms
Possibility to downgrade other participants, volume control
2) more current Linux substructure
-Improve performance with many users, or increase the maximum number of clients
- Provision of a waiting room

2. virtual backgrounds
Functions for productive monitoring of the functional efficiency (monitoring of malfunctions of rooms, sound connections, video connections, etc.)
- Whiteboard is unreliable when using text boxes, live and in recordings text parts can be cut off, sometimes even if they can be seen properly live
- Performance optimizations for end devices
more breakout rooms
Adaptation to the performance of the end devices (avoid AV interference from overloaded end devices, prioritizing audio)

The nominations on place 3 are:

Virtual background or blur
Scalability
- Break-Out Rooms
- More convenience/features, e.g. saving the whiteboard or even whiteboard within a screen sharing
Significantly better update quality - many updates damage configurations
- more current Linux versions as installation basis
- Improvement of usability (clarity of setting and operating options)
Fix: Fix of the power dip introduced with 2.2.28
Usability 1: Separation of chat and notes in a separate window
Stability
Integration of a configurable watermark (copyright) in video stream (presentation) and video downloads
Breakout rooms are unstable with us
Video Transcoding
Performance Issues at Large Meetings
-Accelerated "Echo Check"!
System security - current operating system and components
Download possibility of all session contents (whitescreen, chats etc.)
Display options of current load (number of participants / videos / screenshare) on a server within participating rooms
3. limitation of the maximum number of webcams per session depending on the number of participants - e.g. only 1 webcam for > 150 participants (to avoid operating errors)
- Possibility of integrating other media formats (audio, video with sound)
3. when recording, many teachers would like to have a simple download of the video as mp4 or webx.
Break-out rooms
preload breakout rooms and surveys
- More visible opportunity to actively participate in meetings (raise hand function)
* more breakout rooms
Embedding of IFRAMES (extensions, ...)
3) faster audio switching from breakout to default session (without echo test)
-Save polls, chats and shared notes before the end of the conference
- Performance improvements for larger conferences with several hundred participants

Improvement of the sound quality (level, suppression of background noise)
Support of more device types (Apple, mobile devices)
- Workflow for converting recordings or developing a player to play recordings offline
- Storage of BBB recordings in Opencast including metadata for further processing (mp4) and distribution (streaming)
Change background (https://www.uni-goettingen.de/de/document/download/bd3fd4f285adc6e79c043d44b186009a.pdf/Virtuelle_Hintergrund_Snap_Camera.pdf)
Status message/warning to end user about connection quality (see bar at zoom)

In the appendix, all mentions are listed in context.

3. Would you participate in joint development projects? If so, what financial contribution could you make to a jointly coordinated development?

To this question 23 participants answered with a clear "Yes".

Figure 2: Possibility of financial participation

Out of 56 answers, 23 participants expressed that a financial contribution would be conceivable and 15 named a concrete amount.

Figure 3: Possible amounts of a financial participation

The statements on the amount of financial contributions fluctuate very strongly between one-time or annual participations of 1,000€ up to annual participations of 50,000€.

The average of the mentioned amounts is 11.433€, the median is 10.000€. The total amount of the mentioned participations is about 170.000€.

The individual answers are listed below.

(Names of persons and institutions were removed).

We would bring in capacity for coordination.
We could bring in about 20.000€ p.a. for this.
Only if the application scenario and the differentiation from available solutions is clear. If the intended solution completely replaces Zoom (also in the perception of all users and not only data protection ideologists), we would contribute 50T€ per year as long as online teaching is widely used because of Corona. Afterwards 5T€.
yes, but scope depends on internal agreements/proposals. sometimes 500, sometimes 5.000
I can't put a precise figure on it, but a truly productive development process would definitely be worth our involvement with financial or human resources.
We can imagine a participation and explicitly welcome a coordinated development. However, it is not possible to promise an amount within the framework of this survey.
annual contribution between 5 T€ and 10 T€
approx. €1.000,- to max. €2.000,- per year.
1.000,-- to 2.000,-- per year
Gladly, a one-time amount would be easier to regulate in terms of budgetary law.
possibly
2000 EUR per year
10 thousand
Basically very gladly.
We have no development capacity but we would participate financially. An annual amount of 5.000-10.000€ would be conceivable.
For personnel (but also financial) reasons: Unfortunately "no".
Only a first approach: Each HS/Uni involved finances the equivalent of 1 or more daily rates of a developer
Financing of one (1) daily rate (up to about 1.500€) as equivalent for 1 PT/month
Yes. once 3.000€
difficult to say, depends on the scope of services / developments / support - e.g. 1.000 EUR per year conceivable
No, our university is too small for that.
After consultation with the presidium of the university, cooperation would be possible if necessary. The financial contribution to be made is also to be agreed upon within the university.
In principle yes, but no funds are planned
The faculty would participate in joint development projects with an annual contribution in the range of 5000-10000 Euro.
In principle, we would want to participate financially. Exact amounts I cannot name. One-time as well as annual participations are possible.
We are not yet able to provide any figures on this at present. Should we decide to make BBB available in a permanent productive way, we could imagine the also permanent participation in a jointly organized further development and mutual support, which is e.g. institutionalized as an association (see DSpace, Moodle, etc.).
Annually up to 1 Euro per student (35.000 Euro/a)
One-time financial participation safely possible. Recurring financial participation likely possible.
Introduction of requirements including discussion and prioritization very well possible.
Yes, about 10.000,-€/year.

The university would participate financially in joint development projects. Financial possibilities still have to be clarified internally.

Financial participation is difficult, but we may be able to contribute personnel.

4. Would you like to be included in the list of interested parties for BBB activities?

43 participants have given their addresses for further participation.

5. Appendix

The names of the desired functions are:

<p>Integration of telephone dial-in Improvement of the audio quality Virtual background or blur Message function that is faded into the video Support of more participants per conference</p>
<p>Resource requirements on the end devices are too high, only relatively up-to-date and high-performance devices allow for low-disturbance participation</p>
<p>Scalability Scalability Scalability User Acceptance</p>
<p>- Audio Quality - Scalability - Break-Out Rooms</p>
<p>Meetings with > 50 participants</p>
<p>- Recording option in compliance with data protection laws, if necessary via Opencast (https://weblog.lkiesow.de/20200318-integrate-bigbluebutton-opencast/), recording and processing as external as possible- More flexibility, e.g. quick change of microphone or webcam or the splitting/arrangement of videos or video/presentations- More convenience/features, e.g. saving the whiteboard or whiteboard in general within a screen sharing</p>
<p>Support of current infrastructure / operating systems More awareness of the topic of data protection (recording function, mute button, deletion periods). Significantly better update quality - many updates damage configurations Better logging - troubleshooting is incredibly tedious Admin presetting for password obligation and similar presets as with zoom Prioritization Adjust image/sound so that sound always remains stable (Better) Functioning connection to RocketChat</p>
<p>- better scaling with the number of video streams (possibly similar to Jitsi Videobridge) - people want to turn on the webcams and see each other, they are used to that as standard from other platforms - deployment as docker container with docker composite - more current Linux versions as installation basis - faster reaction to contributions of the developer community - central configuration files, which are not overwritten with updates - better usable whiteboard (storage possibility of contents, eraser function, palm recognition on Tablets)</p>
<p>- Possibility to work with larger groups of participants (more than 200 participants) (see problems at the ILIAS DE conference)</p> <p>- Improvement of the login process (incl. audio/video connection)</p> <p>- Improvement of usability (clarity of setting and operating options)</p>

<p>New load distribution algorithm for Scalelite (under development) Fix: Fix of stability problems introduced with 2.2.28 Fix: Fix of power loss introduced with 2.2.28 Increase of the maximum number of participants per conference from 120 to at least 200 (will only be possible with BBB 2.3) Transfer of affiliations and groups when registering via Shibboleth/LdapExtended role concept (maximum conference size, etc. depending on affiliations) Support of server class reservation system (exclusive use of servers for important conferences)</p>
<p>Stability and performance improvement, even when including end devices with weak network connectivity / low performance Faster bug fixing Usability 1: Separation of chat and notes in separate window Usability 2: Emoji tools such as thumbs up</p>
<p>Scaling for large groups, more flexible breakout rooms (number, communication into the rooms); stability</p>
<p>Stability improvement of the current version (2.2.28) Sound transmission during screen sharing Integration of a configurable watermark (copyright) in video stream (presentation) and video downloads Simple download of annotated slides (presentations) Selection/modification of microphone and camera after entering a room Naming of breakout rooms Improved survey tool (more question types, more options)</p>
<p>- Stability and availability - user friendliness</p>
<p>- Quality in audio and video, as noise is often present - recording function should at least provide the result as a download</p>
<p>Increase of the maximum number of participants</p>
<p>Statistics Features Manageability Breakout rooms are unstable</p>
<p>Screen Sharing, IOS Sharing, Video Transcoding</p>
<p>Stability Diagnosis possibility for users to find out where their connection problem is (like test.webrtc.org on the BBB server) Download performance issues for large meeting recordings</p>
<p>- Improving connectivity behind restrictive firewalls (TURN server)</p>
<p>The only officially supported installation method of Greenlight is with Docker. Since BBB itself can also be installed manually, it is a pity that this is not possible with Greenlight. When using LDAP authentication, it is not possible to make an assignment to LDAP fields because they are hardcoded. For example, Greenlight assumes that the full name of a user is in the LDAP field "cn". If this is not given in your own directory service, the code must be adapted within the Docker image.</p>
<p>-Export presentations with created sketches to BBB. -Change background for camera.</p>

<p>-Accelerated "Echo Check"! -E-mail the BBB link directly from Greenlight to users.</p> <p>-List view for BBB rooms in Greenlight.</p> <p>-Sort server rooms by status and participants in Greenlight.</p>
<p>Performance- Multithreading/Multitasking to achieve a better hardware utilization</p> <p>Performance- Support larger conference sizes / (Depends on server hardware)</p> <p>System security - current operating system and componentsClient</p> <p>- background blur to hide environment</p>
<p>We lack the possibility to record BBB - sessions to make them available to the students.</p>
<p>Since no deployment is planned (we already supervise DFNConf, zoom, lecture recording, lecture hall technology in a minimum number of participants), we have no need for improvements</p>
<p>Better quality of sound and video Higher tolerance of bandwidth fluctuations, reconnectDownload possibility of all session contents (whitescreen, chats etc.)</p> <p>Improved usability in general, more modern look and feel automatic. Foreground switching of the share Participant individual virtual image background</p>
<p>1. the dependence on local conditions2 . Dependence on different browser versions3 .</p>
<p>Group size up to 300 participants stable possible</p>
<p>Post-synchronization of recording tracksRecording processing on separate serversDisplay options of current load (number of participants / videos / screenshare) on a server within participating rooms</p> <p>Current operating system / componentsHigher maximum number of participants</p>
<p>1. load distribution between BBB nodes based on parameters such as expected number of participants, not only on number of webconf per node2 . Better behavior in case of high server load - e.g. regulation of webcam quality based on server load up to the shutdown of webcams3 . Limitation of the max. number of webcams per session based on the number of participants - e.g. only 1 webcam for > 150 participants (avoiding misuse)4. optimization CPU load with many webcams => there the zoom-client is less resource-hungry (although not the zoom-webclient)5. optimization bandwidth requirement for screen sharing => 1-2Mbps is too much for home office (16 Mbps DSL: max. 1Mbps in uplink)6. sound also for desktop audio</p>
<p>I can't estimate this yet.</p>
<p>- definable participation limit, which cannot be overwritten by connected systems- stability- integration of further media formats (audio, video with sound)</p> <p>- better documentation with the BBB-install.sh script (e.g. option -d)</p> <p>- free choice of the install folder</p>
<p>1. currently the number of participants in a video conference (depending on chats, cameras, etc.) is limited to about 170 participants. This limitation occurs due to internal mechanisms of BBB and should be increased significantly.</p> <p>2. in the standard configuration of Big Blue Button, video conferences are always recorded https://www.golem.de/news/big-blue-button-das-grosse-blaue-sicherheitsrisiko-2010-151610-5.html. The recording function should be DSGVO-compliant and only take place when recording is selected.</p>

<p>3. when recording, many teachers wish to have a simple download of the video as mp4 or webx.</p> <p>4. integrated streaming function, i.e. the teacher can say: video conference also streaming, a link is displayed which can be distributed.</p> <p>5. further development of the whiteboard functions, for example: https://openboard.ch/index.de.html</p>
<p>Resource requirement Client, so that conferences with several participants and video also workBackground selectable as with ZoomBreak-out rooms</p>
-
<p>Feature for lectures and other presentations: instead of automatic activation of the lecturer's microphone as was previously the case with BBB, manual, permanent activation of the microphone should be made possible.</p>
<p>integrate computersound easy sharing of audios, also TN-side pre-loading of breakout rooms and survey easy hand lifting</p>
<p>- Higher possible number of users- Better audio quality- Visible possibility to actively participate in meetings (raise hand function) - Setting the background with an image (as with zoom)</p>
<p>* stable and reliable availability* faster changeover to breakout rooms* more breakout rooms</p>
<p>Settings that survive a room sessionPossibility to control down other participants, volume controlEmbedding of IFRAMES (extensions, ...) Live migration of BBB sessions between hosts (heartbeat, high availability) similar to VMWare ESXi Live MigrationsUbuntu 20.04 LTS base system</p>
<p>We heard about scaling problems and clear limitations in terms of conference size. We have seminars with up to 1000 participants and many seminars with between 100-500 participants.</p>
<p>1) more breakout sessions2) newer Linux substructure3) faster audio switching from breakout to default session (without echo test)</p>
<p>-Securely deploy recordings (with permission checking) - Improve performance for large numbers of users or increase the maximum number of clients - Secure polls , chats and shared notes before the end of the conference -16:9 support of camera breakout rooms can be renamed</p>
<p>- Possibility to rename breakout rooms - Provision of a waiting room</p>

- Performance improvements for larger conferences with several hundred participants
- Whiteboard: Eraser
- Whiteboard: Make text fields editable
- Whiteboard: Multi-user sharing for all pages of a document
- Screen transmission including system audio (as in Jitsi)
- Dedicated audio channels for interpreters*
- Download rights can only be changed by the original uploader of the document
- Automatic provision of a log file (with chat, notes and participants) when a conference is ended

1. stronger compression of the meeting data to enable better performance even with lower bandwidth (WLAN usage)²
 - . virtual backgrounds
3. hand lift button easier to reach⁴
 - . separate moderator chat⁵
 - . SIP integration⁶
 - . easier streaming of meetings
7. better survey function (also anonymous)
8. configuration possibility for rooms (incl. templates) already during room creation (e.g. whiteboard hidden)

Improvement of sound quality (level, suppression of background noise)
 Functions for productive monitoring of the functionality (monitoring of malfunctions of rooms, sound connections, video connections etc.)
 Support of more device types (Apple, mobile devices)
 Video processing on the server to reduce load on the clients
 DSGVO compliant data processing (e.g. Video recording only on demand, no recording of chat)
 Improved rights management for shared recordings
 Better reconnect on disconnected connections (without having to leave the room and re-enter)
 Multiple BBB clusters in Moodle (BBB Moodle plugin)
 Export of video recordings to MP4
 Better administration features (better installation pipeline, comprehensive admin dashboard, migration of rooms etc.)

- possibly speed up release of 2.3, for example to be able to use the announced "raise hand" notification as soon as possible-
- Whiteboard is unreliable when using text boxes, live and in recordings text parts can be cut off, sometimes even if they can be seen properly live-
- Workflow for converting recordings or development of a player to be able to play recordings offline

- Stability fixes for larger events-
- Performance optimizations for end devices-
- Storage of BBB recordings in Opencast including metadata for further processing (mp4) and distribution (streaming)
- More secure sharing of videos (e.g. via "split screen" in two variants: Video.720p/25FPS and Powerpoint.1080p/5FPS)
- Transmission of audio via "split screen"
- Option: Flip webcam image-
- Separate report button (currently difficult to access and not barrier-free)
- Option: Export whiteboard to save results-
- Option: Blur background in webcam image for privacy

Play audio and video files directly from your local computer without having to upload them to a streaming server (in great demand!)

more Breakout

RoomsChange your

breakout room background

([https://www.uni-](https://www.uni-goettingen.de/de/document/download/bd3fd4f285adc6e79c043d44b186009a.pdf/Virtuelle_Hintergrund_Snap_Camera.pdf)

[goettingen.de/de/document/download/bd3fd4f285adc6e79c043d44b186009a.pdf/Virtuelle_Hintergrund_Snap_Camera.pdf](https://www.uni-goettingen.de/de/document/download/bd3fd4f285adc6e79c043d44b186009a.pdf/Virtuelle_Hintergrund_Snap_Camera.pdf))

Scalability of the server (reliable execution of large events)

Adaptation to the performance of the end devices (avoid AV disturbances by overloaded end devices, prioritize audio)

Status message/ warning to end users regarding the connection quality (see bar at zoom)

Speaker-related control of the video size including adaptation of the resolution/frame rate/bit rate (i.e. current speaker large/high quality, listener small/low quality).

Optional control of the layout at the participants by the moderator

(whiteboard/chat/notes/show/hide list of participants)

Additional layout options (presentation/video left/right or presentation with picture-in-picture, see zoom)

Still image/avatars when the camera is offSolution

for distribution of recordings (complete interface to Opencast or export of the recording as 1 video file)

Interface to video conference systems (H.323 gateway)

Extend whiteboard functionalities (insert images, post-it cards (see Flinga-Board), export as . pdf, save option for follow-up processing at a later date)

Poll functionalities (anonymous survey, additional question types, more than 5 answer options (already configurable))

Resource hunger, especially network load and GPU load on the clients